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Alterations in the Corpuscles of Stannius after Estradiol Administration to Stinging Fish, *Heteropneustes fossilis* Maintained in Different Calcium Environments

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Abstract: In the present study, the effects of estradiol administration have been investigated on plasma calcium, plasma phosphate and corpuscles of Stannius of a teleost, *Heteropneustes fossilis*. The fishes were procured and divided into 4 numerically equal groups (A-D). The fish from group A were given a single intraperitoneal injection of vehicle (0.1 ml of groundnut oil/100 g body wt) and kept in artificial freshwater. Fish from group B were given a single intraperitoneal injection of estradiol (1 mg/100 g body wt) and kept in artificial freshwater. Fish from group C were given a single intraperitoneal injection of vehicle (0.1 ml of ground nut oil/100 g body wt) and kept in calcium-deficient freshwater. Fish from group D were given a single intraperitoneal injection of estradiol (1 mg/100 g body wt) and kept in calcium-deficient freshwater. Blood samples were taken after 1, 3, 5, 10 and 15 days following the treatment. After collection of blood samples, corpuscles of Stannius were fixed.

Group A & B (Artificial freshwater): In group A, the plasma calcium levels of vehicle-injected fish exhibit almost no change throughout the experiment. In group B, Estradiol treatment caused hypercalcemia from day 3 to day 10, however, after day 15 the level slightly decreased; whereas hyperphosphatemia was observed from day 3 till the close of the experiment.

There is no change in the CS of vehicle-injected fish (group A) throughout the experiment. In group B, the corpuscular cells exhibit no histological change up to day 3 following estradiol treatments. From day 5 to day 10 there is a progressive increase in the AF-positive granules. On these intervals the nuclear volume of AF-positive cells does not show any change. On day 15, there is a slight decrease in the staining response of the cytoplasm of AF-positive cells. The nuclear volume still remains unchanged. The AF-negative cells of estradiol treated fish (group B) exhibit no histological change throughout the experiment.

Group C & D (Calcium-deficient freshwater): The plasma calcium level of vehicle-injected fish (group C) exhibits a slight decrease on day 1 which continued till day 3. Thereafter, the plasma calcium level records an increase from day 5 resulting in hypercalcemia on day 10 and day 15. The plasma calcium levels of estradiol treated fish (group D) exhibits no change at day 1. Estradiol treatment caused a progressive increase in the plasma calcium level from day 3 to day 15. In group C, a progressive hypophosphatemia is recorded from day 3 to day 5. On day 10 and day 15, the phosphate level indicates a tendency to increase. In group D, the estradiol treated fish exhibited no change in the plasma phosphate level up to day 3. Thereafter, from day 5 till the close of the experiment the plasma phosphate level exhibits an increase.

The corpuscular cells of vehicle-injected fish (group C) exhibit no histological change on day 1. There is a progressive increase in the AF-positive granules between day 3 and day 5. The nuclear volume of AF-positive cells exhibits no change. On day 10 and 15, there is a slight decrease in the staining response of the cytoplasm of AF-positive cells. The nuclear volume at these intervals remains unchanged. The AF-negative cells of vehicle-injected specimens (group C) remain unchanged on day 1. Between day 3 and day 5 a decrease in the nuclear volume of these cells has been recorded. From day 10 to day 15 the nuclear volume exhibits an increase thus approaching to the normal values. In group D, there is no histological change in the corpuscular cells of estradiol-treated fish. From day 5 to day 10 there is accumulation of AF-positive granules. The nuclear volume remains unchanged. On day 15 the AF-positive cells exhibit a decrease in the staining response. The nuclear volume remains unchanged. No histological change has been noticed in the AF-negative cells of estradiol-treated fish (group D).

Key words: estradiol, corpuscles of Stannius, plasma calcium, plasma phosphate, fish

Introduction

The endocrine systems for calcium regulation differ between aquatic and land vertebrates. Fish possess unique and more complex system than the terrestrial vertebrates as they (fish) are in constant contact with surrounding water (either freshwater or seawater) which provides an inexhaustible supply of calcium, thus in most cases facing considerable calcium gradients across the body surface. This situation is very much different in land vertebrates where direct exchange of calcium between the body and surrounding medium is not possible and they have to rely solely on the food for calcium. In them calcium homeostasis is achieved mainly by a balance between intestinal calcium absorption and renal calcium excretion.

Fish regulate their blood calcium level very efficiently. The regulation of calcium homeostasis in fishes involves a number of hormones secreted by different endocrine glands. Pituitary (through prolactin) takes the responsibility of releasing the hypercalcemic factor (s) in the absence of parathyroid gland (which secretes hypercalcemic principle in land vertebrates). Also vitamin D metabolites have been reported as a hypercalcemic factor in fishes (Srivastav, 1983, 1989; Srivastav and Srivastav, 1988; Srivastav and Singh, 1989, 1992; Srivastav *et al.*, 1995, 1998). In fishes, the hypocalcemic factors are released conjointly from the ultimobranchial gland (UBG) and the corpuscles of Stannius (CS) (which is found only in this group). Thus, in fish calcium homeostasis is governed by the pituitary, ultimobranchial gland, corpuscles of Stannius and vitamin D metabolites. The interplay of the hormones released by these endocrine glands at various target organs (skin, fin, gut, gill, bone, and kidney) is responsible for fish calcium homeostasis.

Several studies have implicated the corpuscles of Stannius in the control of calcemia in teleost fishes. There is a close

relationship between the calcium concentration of the ambient water and the secretory activity of the type-1 (AF-positive) cells of the CS. As demonstrated with light and electron microscopy, these cells became activated upon transfer of the fish from freshwater (with moderate to low calcium levels) to seawater (Wendelaar Bonga and Pang, 1986). The CS were also activated in calcium-rich freshwater (Wendelaar Bonga and Pang, 1986; Srivastav and Srivastav, 1988; Singh and Srivastav, 1996) but not in calcium-deficient seawater (Cohen *et al.*, 1975). Increased activity of the CS in seawater was further indicated by the high immunoreactive stanniocalcin levels as observed in the blood/plasma of seawater eel (Wendelaar Bonga and Pang, 1991).

Although the CS is found exclusively in the holostean and teleostean fishes, its hypocalcemic action has also been reported from non-piscine vertebrates – rat (Leung and Fenwick, 1978), parrot (Srivastav and Swarup, 1982) and anurans (Pandey *et al.*, 1982). Recent studies have also indicated that stanniocalcin is of wider occurrence than previously thought. Immunocytochemically stanniocalcin has been localized in the kidney of human and other mammals (Chang *et al.*, 1995; Olsen *et al.*, 1996; de Niu *et al.*, 1998). Moreover, Zhang *et al.* (1998) have reported expression, purification, characterization and bioassay of human stanniocalcin. Worthington *et al.* (1999) have reported expression and localization of stanniocalcin 1 in rat bladder, kidney and ovary.

Vitellogenin (an egg yolk precursor protein) is synthesized in the liver and released into the circulation (Baily, 1957; Chen, 1983; Bjornsson and Haux, 1985; Kwon *et al.*, 1993). Circulating vitellogenin is transported to the ovaries where it is taken up by the developing oocytes and stored as yolk (Persson *et al.*, 1994, 1995; Yeo and Mugiya, 1997). Vitellogenin is a calcium-binding protein – phospholipid-

glycolipoprotein complex and its synthesis may be induced by estradiol-17 β . During vitellogenesis, there is an increase in the protein bound plasma calcium fraction whereas the plasma ionized calcium remains unaffected. The increased plasma calcium level during vitellogenesis has been correlated with the enhanced synthesis of vitellogenin which binds calcium ions. Gillespie and Peyster (2004) have reported the significant linear correlations between plasma vitellogenin and plasma calcium for males, females and males and females combined fathead minnows. Thus, there is an increased calcium demand during vitellogenesis which has to be taken either from the environment, from intestinal uptake and/or from the internal calcium reservoirs.

There exists controversy regarding the source of additional calcium needed after estradiol-induced vitellogenesis in fishes. Increased calcium uptake from environment (Fleming *et al.*, 1964; Persson *et al.*, 1994) and mobilization from scales (Mugiya and Watabe, 1977; Carragher and Sumpter, 1991; Persson *et al.*, 1994, 1995), from muscles (Persson *et al.*, 1994) and from bile (Mugiya and Hazama, 1994) have been reported after estradiol treatment in fishes. The calcium mobilization from scales is suggested to be mediated by estrogen receptors (ER). Pinto *et al.* (2009) have immunohistochemically localized ER α , ER β a and ER β b proteins in scales of juvenile and adult sea bream (*Sparus auratus*) and Mozambique tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*). Pinto *et al.* (2009) have suggested that the calcium mobilizing action of 17 β -estradiol on fish scales is through its direct action on ERs present in osteoblasts. Moreover, estradiol treatment to the fish has been reported not to affect the calcium uptake from the environment (Mugiya and Ichii, 1980), muscle (Carragher and Sumpter, 1991) or bone resorption (Mugiya and Watabe, 1977; Carragher and Sumpter, 1991; Persson *et al.*, 1994), intestinal calcium uptake (Mugiya and Ichii, 1980) and

calcium excretion (Carragher and Sumpter, 1991; Persson *et al.*, 1994).

With this background an attempt has been made in the present study to investigate the effects of estradiol administration in the catfish, *Heteropneustes fossilis* maintained either in artificial freshwater or calcium-deficient freshwater. The changes induced experimentally by this hormone in the plasma calcium and phosphate levels have been correlated with the activity of calcium regulating endocrine gland namely corpuscles of Stannius.

Materials and Methods

Live specimens of freshwater catfish *Heteropneustes fossilis* (both sexes; body wt. 27-39 g) were collected locally and acclimatized to laboratory conditions for two weeks in plastic pools. The water was half renewed daily and the fish were fed on dry shrimp powder. For experiments the fish were kept in identical glass aquaria each containing 10 litres of the medium. 12 fish were kept in each aquarium. The medium was replaced on alternate days. After acclimation they were divided into 4 numerically equal groups (A-D). They were given the following treatments:

Group A: Fish from this group were given a single intraperitoneal injection of vehicle (0.1 ml of groundnut oil/100 g body wt) and kept in artificial freshwater.

Group B: Fish from this group were given a single intraperitoneal injection of estradiol (1 mg/100 g body wt) and kept in artificial freshwater.

Group C: Fish from this group were given a single intraperitoneal injection of vehicle (0.1 ml of ground nut oil/100 g body wt) and kept in calcium-deficient freshwater.

Group D: Fish from this group were given a single intraperitoneal injection of estradiol (1 mg/100 g body wt) and kept in calcium-deficient freshwater.

Estradiol used in groups B and D were dissolved in groundnut oil. Fish were not fed 24 h before and during the experiment.

Different artificial media i.e. freshwater and calcium-deficient freshwater were prepared as follows:

- (a) Artificial freshwater: Distilled water containing (in mmol/liter): NaCl 2.10; Na₂SO₄ 0.45; KCl 0.06; CaCl₂ 0.8; MgCl₂ 0.20. pH of the solution was adjusted to 7.6 with NaHCO₃.
- (b) Calcium-deficient freshwater: same as artificial freshwater without CaCl₂.

Twelve fishes from each group were anaesthetized with MS 222 and blood samples were taken after 1, 3, 5, 10 and 15 days following the treatment. Blood samples were collected in heparinized tubes by sectioning of the caudal peduncle. The plasma were separated by centrifugation and analyzed for calcium and phosphate levels by Sigma kits. After collection of blood samples, the corpuscles of Stannius (CS) along with adjoining portion of kidney were removed and fixed in aqueous Bouin's fluid. Tissues were routinely processed in graded series of alcohols, cleared in xylene and embedded in paraffin. Serial sections were cut at 6 µm. The corpuscles of Stannius were stained with aldehyde fuchsin (AF) and hematoxylin-eosin (HE).

Nuclear indices (maximal length and maximal width) were determined (50 nuclei were measured per specimen, thus 300 nuclei were measured from six specimens) with the aid of ocular micrometer and then nuclear volume was calculated as:

$$\text{Volume} = 4/3 \pi ab^2$$

Where 'a' is the major semiaxis and 'b' is the minor semiaxis.

Data were presented as the mean ± S.E. of six specimens and Student's t-test was used to determine statistical significance. Each experimental group was compared to its specific time control group.

Observations

(A) Artificial freshwater (groups A and B):

The plasma calcium levels of vehicle-injected fish (group A) exhibit almost no change throughout the experiment (Fig. 1).

No significant change has been noticed in the plasma calcium level after day 1

following estradiol treatment (group B). Estradiol treatment caused a progressive increase in the plasma calcium level from day 3 to day 10, however, after day 15 the level slightly decreased (Fig. 1).

There is almost no change in the plasma phosphate levels of vehicle-injected fish (group A) throughout the experiment (Fig. 2).

The plasma phosphate level of estradiol treated fish (group B) remains unchanged up to day 1. Thereafter, from day 3 till the close of the experiment the plasma phosphate level exhibits an increase (Fig. 2).

There is no change in the CS of vehicle-injected fish (group A) throughout the experiment (Fig. 3).

In group B, the corpuscular cells exhibit no histological change up to day 3 following estradiol treatments. From day 5 to day 10 there is a progressive increase in the AF-positive granules (Fig. 4). On these intervals the nuclear volume of AF-positive cells does not show any change (Fig. 5). On day 15, there is a slight decrease in the staining response of the cytoplasm of AF-positive cells (Fig. 6). The nuclear volume still remains unchanged (Fig. 5).

The AF-negative cells of estradiol treated fish (group B) exhibit no histological change throughout the experiment (Fig. 7).

Figure 1: Changes in the plasma calcium levels of *Heteropneustes fossilis*. Group A (vehicle + artificial freshwater), Group B (estradiol + artificial freshwater), Group C (vehicle + calcium deficient freshwater), and Group D (estradiol + calcium deficient freshwater). Each value represents mean ± S.E. of six specimens. Asterisk indicates significant differences ($P < 0.05$) (Group B compared with Group A; Group D compared with Group C).

Figure 2. Changes in the plasma phosphate levels of *Heteropneustes fossilis*. Group A (vehicle + artificial freshwater), Group B (estradiol + artificial freshwater), Group C (vehicle + calcium deficient freshwater), and Group D (estradiol + calcium deficient freshwater). Each value represents mean \pm S.E. of six specimens. Asterisk indicates significant differences ($P < 0.05$) (Group B compared with Group A; Group D compared with Group C).

Figure 3. Corpuscles of Stannius of 5 day vehicle-injected *Heteropneustes fossilis* kept in artificial freshwater depicting AF-positive and AF-negative cells. AF x 800.

Figure 4. Corpuscles of Stannius of 10 day estradiol treated fish kept in artificial freshwater exhibiting increased granulation in AF-positive cells. AF x 800.

Figure 5. Nuclear volume of AF-positive cells of CS of *Heteropneustes fossilis*. Group A (vehicle + artificial freshwater), Group B (estradiol + artificial freshwater), Group C (vehicle + calcium deficient freshwater), and Group D (estradiol + calcium deficient freshwater). Each value represents mean \pm S.E. of six specimens.

Figure 6. Corpuscles of Stannius of 15 day estradiol treated *Heteropneustes fossilis* kept in artificial freshwater showing slight degranulation of AF-positive cells. AF x 800.

Figure 7. Nuclear volume of AF-negative cells of CS of *Heteropneustes fossilis*. Group A (vehicle + artificial freshwater), Group B (estradiol + artificial freshwater), Group C (vehicle + calcium deficient freshwater), and Group D (estradiol + calcium deficient freshwater). Each value represents mean \pm S.E. of six specimens.

(B) Calcium deficient freshwater (groups C and D):

The plasma calcium level of vehicle-injected fish (group C) exhibits a slight decrease on day 1 (as compared with the level of the fish kept in artificial freshwater at day 1). This response continues till day 3. Thereafter, the plasma calcium level records an increase from day 5 resulting in hypercalcemia on day 10 and day 15 (Fig. 1).

The plasma calcium levels of estradiol treated fish (group D) exhibits no change at day 1. Estradiol treatment caused a progressive increase in the plasma calcium level from day 3 to day 15 (Fig. 1).

In vehicle-injected fish (group C), the plasma phosphate level remains unchanged on day 1. From day 3 to day 5, a progressive hypophosphatemia is recorded. On day 10 and day 15, the phosphate level indicates a tendency to increase (Fig. 2).

In estradiol treated fish (group D) the plasma phosphate level remains unchanged up to day 3. Thereafter, from day 5 till the close of the experiment the plasma phosphate level exhibits an increase (Fig. 2). The corpuscular cells of vehicle-injected fish (group C) exhibit no histological change on day 1. There is a progressive increase in the AF-positive granules between day 3 and day 5 (Fig. 8). The nuclear volume of AF-positive cells exhibits no change (Fig. 5). On day 10 and 15, there is a slight decrease in the staining response of the cytoplasm of AF-positive cells (Fig. 9). The nuclear volume at these intervals remains unchanged (Fig. 5).

The AF-negative cells of vehicle-injected specimens (group C) remain unchanged on day 1. Between day 3 and day 5 a decrease in the nuclear volume of these cells (as compared to group A) has been recorded (Fig. 7). From day 10 to day 15 the nuclear volume exhibits an increase thus approaching to the normal values (Fig. 7).

Up to day 3 there is no histological change in the corpuscular cells of estradiol-treated fish (group D). From day 5 to day 10 there is accumulation of AF-positive granules (Fig. 10). The nuclear volume remains unchanged (Fig. 5). On day 15 the

AF-positive cells exhibit a decrease in the staining response (Fig. 11). The nuclear volume remains unchanged (Fig. 5).

No histological change has been noticed in the AF-negative cells of estradiol-treated fish (group D as compared to group C; Fig. 7).

Figure 8. Increased granules in AF-positive cells of CS of 3 day vehicle- injected fish kept in calcium-deficient freshwater. AF x 800.

Figure 9. Slight degranulation in AF-positive cells of CS of 10 day vehicle- injected fish kept in calcium-deficient freshwater. AF x 800.

Figure 10. Accumulation of AF-positive granules in the CS of 5 day estradiol treated fish kept in calcium-deficient freshwater. AF x 800.

Figure 11. Degranulation of the AF-positive cells of CS of 15 day estradiol injected fish maintained in calcium-deficient freshwater. AF x 800.

Discussion

In the present study estradiol treatment caused elevation in the plasma calcium and phosphate levels of the fish kept in artificial freshwater. This is in agreement with previously reported increase in plasma levels of these electrolytes after estradiol treatment (Baily, 1957; Fleming *et al.*, 1964; Yamada *et al.*, 1982; Bjornsson and Haux, 1985; Bjornsson *et al.*, 1989; Norberg *et al.*, 1989; Madsen and Korsgaard, 1991; Mugiya and Hazama, 1994; Persson *et al.*, 1994, 1995). The observed elevation of plasma electrolytes may be attributed to increased mobilization from internal stores. Mobilization of scale calcium has been reported in E₂ (estradiol) treated rainbow trout (Carragher and Sumpter, 1991; Persson *et al.*, 1994) and goldfish and killifish (Mugiya and Watabe, 1977). Persson *et al.* (1994) have noticed calcium mobilization from muscles of E₂ treated rainbow trout. However, the calcium content of muscle, vertebrae, rib bones, jaw or otolith remains unaffected by estradiol treatment (Mugiya and Watabe, 1977; Carragher and Sumpter, 1991).

The increased plasma calcium content in estradiol treated *H. fossilis* could not be attributed to the increased intestinal calcium uptake, as the fish were not fed in the present study.

In calcium-deficient freshwater estradiol administration results into hypercalcemia and hyperphosphatemia.

There exists no report of such a study from teleosts. Since calcium is not available in the surrounding media and also the animals were not fed in the present study, the hypercalcemia observed in estradiol treated *H. fossilis* could not be linked to the calcium absorption at intestinal mucosa. Enhanced calcium uptake from the environment after estradiol injection has been reported from other fish species (Fleming *et al.*, 1964; Persson *et al.*, 1994). In contrast, Mugiya and Ichii (1980) have noticed no effect of estradiol on the *in situ* branchial calcium uptake.

The observed hyperphosphatemia in estradiol treated fish may be explained due to the increased resorption of bone and/or mobilization of phosphate from soft tissues. However, increased branchial phosphate uptake is ruled out as fish gill is incapable of phosphate absorption.

When the fish are kept in calcium deficient freshwater and injected with vehicle the plasma calcium and phosphate levels declined. This derives support from the studies of Wendelaar Bonga *et al.* (1984) who have also noticed hypocalcemia in tilapia after 5 days of its transference to low ambient calcium. This can be attributed to the increased branchial efflux of these ions. Flik *et al.* (1986) have suggested that low calcium concentration in the ambient water of tilapia would allow intracellular Ca⁺⁺ to diffuse out of the animal. Moreover, branchial efflux routes of Ca⁺⁺ following paracellular routes could be increased as a result of lower ambient Ca⁺⁺. The observed hypocalcemia in the fish kept in calcium deficient freshwater also derives support from the studies of Wendelaar Bonga and Van der Meij (1981) as they have noticed increased integumental water permeability at low ambient Ca⁺⁺. This increased water uptake may increase urine production which leads to Ca⁺⁺ loss from the body (Fenwick, 1981).

In the present study the increased granulation in the AF-positive cells of corpuscles of Stannius of estradiol injected fish kept either in artificial freshwater or

calcium deficient freshwater has been noticed. Stanniocalcin – secretion of corpuscles of Stannius has been reported to inhibit the influx of Ca^{++} from the water (Wendelaar Bonga and Pang, 1991; Wagner, 1994).

Considering the hypocalcemic action of stanniocalcin the inhibition of release of secretory granules from the AF-positive cells after estradiol treatment seems reasonable as during vitellogenesis an excessive demand for calcium is needed. This can be obtained by an increased influx of calcium from external reservoir which could be hindered by increased levels of a hypocalcemic hormone stanniocalcin acting mainly on branchial calcium uptake.

Estradiol has been reported to stimulate the activity of corpuscles of Stannius in female catfish (Pandey, 1988). However, similar treatment of gold fish caused no effect in the activity of corpuscles of Stannius (Yamada *et al.*, 1982). Moreover, during the period of rapid ovarian growth the secretory activity of corpuscles of Stannius is elevated (Subhedar and Prasada Rao, 1979; Urasa and Wendelaar Bonga, 1985).

In estradiol treated fish maintained in artificial freshwater and calcium deficient freshwater the AF-positive cells have been noticed to be degranulated. This may be attributed to the persistent elevation of plasma calcium level induced by estradiol.

In vehicle-injected fish kept in calcium deficient freshwater there is an increased storage of AF-positive granules. This may be due to the observed hypocalcemia. Hypoactive type-I cells (AF-positive cells) have been noticed the fish exposed to low calcium seawater (Wendelaar Bonga, 1980). Increased secretory granules in AF-positive cells of CS have also been noticed in the fish which showed hypocalcemia after treatment with various toxicants (Kumar *et al.*, 2013; Prasad *et al.*, 2014; Prakash *et al.*, 2015). In mammals storage of secretory granules within calcitonin cells (which secrete a hypocalcemic factor) has been noticed in response to hypocalcemia (Gittes *et al.*,

1968; Leitz and Donath, 1970; Biddulph and Maibenco, 1972; Swarup *et al.*, 1980; Srivastav and Swarup, 1982). Hirsch and Munson (1969) have suggested that the heavy accumulation of secretory granules in mammalian calcitonin cells during hypocalcemia results due to little or no calcitonin secretion and continuance of its biosynthesis. The same principle seems to be involved in the present study also.

It is of interest to note in the present study that AF-negative cells of vehicle-injected fish exhibit a decreased nuclear volume in calcium deficient freshwater. This reduced activity of AF-negative cells may be attributed to the possible increase in the blood sodium levels as it has been reported that removal of calcium from water bathing the gills of gold fish resulted in a two-fold increase in Na^+ influx (Cutbert and Maetz, 1972).

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